

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF ABS REINFORCED WITH RECYCLED ELIUM THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE

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Introduction

The transport industry is working on promising technologies to minimize fuel consumption and greenhouse effect emissions, while increasing the sustainability of the manufacturing processes. Thermoplastic composites (TPC) are a key technology to achieve these challenges thanks to their ability to be recycled, unlimited shelf life, and excellent mechanical properties in comparison with thermoset matrices [1]. Additionally, two mainstream wastes can be identified in the transport sector: the post-industrial waste generated during the manufacturing process and the post-consumer waste. Elium® is an acrylic reactive-thermoplastic resin that would allow the reuse of these materials wastes in transport secondary applications with full guarantee of life cycle sustainability.

Objectives

Quantify the effect of incorporating recycled Elium® TPC to virgin ABS in the mechanical properties as well as comparing its performance to commercial ABS compounds: virgin ABS (vABS), recycled ABS (rABS) and reinforced ABS with 20% glass fibre.

This study has been developed within the context of the EC-funded Recotrans [2] project, which aims at increasing the sustainability and reducing the production time and cost of RTM processes in the transport industry.

Materials and Methods

Results and Findings

Conclusions

- The recyclability of Elium® based thermoplastics has been demonstrated.
- The tensile strength and the Young's modulus increase linearly with the increase of Elium® composite weight content.
- Impact strength decreases as the weight content of Elium® composite increases.

Acknowledgments:

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References:

- [1] S. Boria, A. Scattina, G. Belingardi "Experimental evaluation of a fully recyclable thermoplastic composite". Composite Structures. Vol 140, pp 21-35, 2016
- [2] <https://recotransproject.eu/>